

[(substituted phenyl)methylene]hydrazide (0.01 mol) dissolved in pyridine. The resulting coloured solid was recrystallised from ethanol (Table 2).

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Synthesis of 3-[4-(4'-Oxothiazolidinyl-2-imino)phenyl]-5,6-dihydro-5-oxothiazolo[2,3-a]triazole and its Diarylidene Derivatives

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ALTHOUGH the synthesis and biological activities¹ of thiazolidinone derivatives have been studied by several investigators, compounds containing two thiazolidinone moieties, one fused to a triazole ring and the other in the form of a side chain are not known. In continuation of our earlier work² of this series we report here the synthesis of compound 4 starting from *p*-aminobenzoylhydrazine (1) which was obtained from *p*-aminobenzoic acid by standard procedure³.

The hydrazine (1) gave 1-(4-thioureidobenzoyl)-thiosemicarbazide (2) after reacting with potassium thiocyanate in concentrated HCl. The thiosemicarbazide, when heated with 10% KOH, furnished

5-(4-thioureidobenzoyl)-2-mercapto-*s*-triazole (3) as crystalline solid. Condensation of 3 with monochloroacetic acid and NaOAc in absolute ethanol gave 3-[4-(4'-oxothiazolidinyl-2-imino)phenyl]-5,6-dihydro-5-oxothiazolo[2,3-*a*]triazole (4). The diarylidene derivatives (5) were synthesised from 4 by reacting with aromatic aldehydes in acetic acid and sodium acetate (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1

The ir spectra of 2 showed a strong carbonyl band at 1 720 cm^{-1} and two broad bands at 3 500–3 150 cm^{-1} corresponding to primary and secondary amino functions. Its cyclised product triazole (3) did not show any carbonyl absorption but a weak band at 2 420 cm^{-1} corresponding to SH confirmed the structure. The thiazolidinone (4) showed two carbonyl absorptions at 1 745 and 1 720 cm^{-1} and the other band at 2 955 cm^{-1} (CH_2). The dibenzylidene derivative (5; $\text{Ar}=\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$) of 4 gave carbonyl absorptions at 1 730 and 1 700 cm^{-1} and the band at 2 955 cm^{-1} was absent. The bathochromic shifts of the carbonyls are due to their conjugation with the oxocyclic double bond.

Experimental

All melting points reported are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 293 spectrophotometer.

1-(4-Thioureidobenzoyl)thiosemicarbazide (2): A mixture of *p*-aminobenzoyl hydrazine (1.5 g, 10 mmol), potassium thiocyanate (4 g, 40 mmol), concentrated HCl (10 ml) and water (50 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. After cooling, the resulting yellow solid was dried and recrystallised from ethanol, (1.57 g, 60%), m p. 200° (Found . S, 23.60 $\text{C}_9\text{N}_5\text{S}_2\text{OH}_{1.1}$ requires : S, 23.79%); ν_{max} 3 500–3 150br (NH, NH_2), 1 680 (C=O), 1 610, 1 590 and 1 440 cm^{-1} .

5-(4-Thioureido)phenyl-2-mercapto-*s*-triazole (3): A mixture of 1-(4-thioureidobenzoyl)thiosemicarbazide (2.7 g, 10 mmol) and 10% KOH solution (30 ml) was refluxed slowly over direct flame for 3 h. The

mixture was then cooled to room temperature and filtered. The filtrate was neutralised by the gradual addition of glacial acetic acid. The resulting colourless solid was dried and recrystallised from ethanol, (1.3 g, 65%), m.p. 250° (Found : S, 25.2. C₉N₅S₂H₉ requires : S, 25.4%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 410–3 100br (NH), 2 420 (SH), 1 600, 1 560 and 1 415 cm⁻¹.

3-[4-(4'-Oxothiazolidinyl-2-imino)phenyl]-5,6-dihydro-5-oxothiazolo[2,3-a]triazole (4) : A mixture of 3 (2.51 g, 10 mmol), monochloroacetic acid (2 g, 20 mmol) and anhydrous NaOAc (0.5 g) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for 4 h. The excess of solvent was then evaporated and the resulting slurry was poured into crushed ice. The resulting light yellow solid was filtered off, dried and recrystallised from ethanol (1.46 g, 50%), m.p. 190° (Found : S, 19.0. C₁₃N₅S₂O₂H₉ requires : S, 19.3%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 210br (NH), 2 955 (CH₂), 1 710 and 1 730 (carbonyls in different environment), 1 600, 1 570 and 1 500 cm⁻¹.

3-[4-(5-Benzylidene-4-oxothiazolidenyl)imino]phenyl-6-benzylidene-5,6-dihydro-5-oxothiazolo[2,3-a]triazole (5; Ar=C₆H₅) : A mixture of 4 (1.1 g, 3 mmol), benzaldehyde (0.7 g, 6 mmol) and anhydrous NaOAc (0.5 g) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was refluxed for 2.5 h. After cooling, the deep yellow solution was poured into crushed ice and the resulting yellow solid was dried and recrystallised from acetic acid (0.65 g, 60%), m.p. 205° (Found : S, 12.4. C₂₇N₅S₂O₂H₁₇ requires : S, 12.6%); $\nu_{\max}$ 3 200br (NH), 1 725 and 1 740 (carbonyls in different environment), 1 620, 1 590, 1 510 and 1 430 cm⁻¹.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE THIAZOLIDINONES (5)

Ar	M.p. °C	Yield %	$\nu_{\max}$ cm ⁻¹	Analysis S% † Found/ (Calcd.)
<i>p</i> -Anisyl	140	66	1 710, 1 730	11.0 (11.20)
<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	128	60	1 720, 1 740	11.01 (11.10)
<i>p</i> -Bromophenyl	146	55	1 715, 1 730	8.86 (9.14)
<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	178	50	1 700, 1 720	9.61 (9.73)

The physical and analytical data of the other diarylidenes are given in Table 1.

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A New Flavonol Glycoside from Guar (*Cyamopsis tetragonoloba* L. Taub)

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IN a previous paper¹, we reported the presence of myricetin-7-glucoside-3-glycoside, kaempferol-7-glucoside-3-glycoside, taxasin-7-O-glucoside and daidzein-7-O-glucoside in guar (*Cyamopsis tetragonoloba* L. Taub), an important legume crop. In the present communication, a new flavonol tetraglycoside has been reported.

Samples (1 kg) of dried, powdered seeds/leaves were refluxed with petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°, 4 dm³) for 4 h. It was followed by two extractions with 80% aqueous methanol (3.5 dm³ each), under reflux for 4 h each time. The combined methanolic extracts were filtered and concentrated to dryness under reduced pressure.

Both one-dimensional and two-dimensional paper chromatography were employed using Whatman no. 1 paper for qualitative purpose and Whatman no. 3 paper for preparative work. The solvent systems used were: butan-1-ol–acetic acid–water (4 : 1 : 5, v/v/v) and aqueous acetic acid (2.2%, v/v).

The specific detecting reagents used were (i) FeCl₃–K₃Fe(CN)₆: phenolic compounds, (ii) ethanolic 1% (w/w) AlCl₃: flavonols, (iii) ethanolic 1% (w/w) FeCl₃: di-OH-phenolics, (iv) sodium metaperiodate benzidine reagent²: phenolic glycosides, and (v) aniline hydrogen phthalate: reducing sugars.

Acid hydrolysis of flavonol glycoside (Found : C, 50.03; H, 5.3. C₃₉H₅₀O₂₆ requires : C, 50.1; H, 5.35%) was carried out in 95% ethanol–2M HCl (1 : 1) at 100° for 1 h. Aglycones were detected under uv light whereas sugars were identified by spraying aniline hydrogen phthalate reagent³. Partial hydrolysis was carried out in 1M HCl for